

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D5.8 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION ACTIVITIES REPORT V1

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP 5
Task	Task 5.1
Due date	31/03/2022
Submission date	11/04/2022
Deliverable lead	Martel Innovate
Version	0.1
Authors	Galileo Disperati, Clementina Piani (Martel Innovate), Dr. Tanja Deuerling (NMA), Lina Silveira (F6S), Wim Vanobberghen (VRT), Marianne Fjellhaug (MCB), Carmela Asero (EBU), Sten Saluveer (Storytek)
Reviewers	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

Abstract	<i>This document describes the STADIEM communication and impact creation activities (T5.1) carried out during the first half of the project. Thanks to a close monitoring of KPIs and achievements, this document provides an overview of the activities implemented based on the strategy and plans outlined in D5.2 and the plan for the second half of the project.</i>
Keywords	Dissemination, Communication, Community Building, Next Generation Media, Open Calls promotion, Networking, Innovators, Impact.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
v0.1	15/03/2022	ToC and first editing	Galileo Disperati, Clementina Piani (Martel Innovate)
v0.2	29/03/2022	Integration of partners' contribution	Dr. Tanja Deuerling (NMA), Lina Silveira (F6S), Wim Vanobberghen (VRT), Marianne Fjellhaug (MCB), Carmela Asero (EBU), Sten Saluveer (Storytek)
v0.3	04/04/2022	Internal Review	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)
v0.4	11/04/2022	Final version	Galileo Disperati (Martel Innovate)

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable describes how STADIEM has followed, in the reporting period M1-M18, a comprehensive and effective approach to dissemination, communication and community building activities, based upon the strategy defined in Deliverable [D5.2: Outreach and Impact Creation Strategy and Plan](#).

In the first half of the project, the consortium has harvested fruitful results from a wide range of dissemination, promotional and engagement activities. The different communication channels and dissemination tools identified at the beginning of the project were used to promote the activities, results and the Open Calls carried by STADIEM project. The key results are listed as follows:

- STADIEM strengthened its online presence featuring quality content on the project's activities and results, animating its social media channels and creating multimedia promotional tools.
- STADIEM created 22 videos featuring project activities, partners and engaged start-ups/scale-ups, reaching over 1,800 views.
- In total, STADIEM has widely promoted its results and activities to more than 1,000,000 stakeholders (including subscribers to social media channels, website visitors and mailing lists, greatly thanks to the Open Calls promotion).
- STADIEM press releases were distributed to over 150 specialized media contacts.
- STADIEM has participated in 10 major relevant events and presented itself to relevant stakeholders.

The collaboration among all partners allowed the project to maintain a high level of communication intensity despite the ongoing COVID-19 emergency, which caused some delays and several relevant events cancellations.

For the second half the project, the strategic perspective of the STADIEM outreach and impact creation effort will continue to serve the overall success of the project and maximize the dissemination and communication impact within the communities of target stakeholders. Such effort includes:

- Continuation of the active communication and promotion of the project activities, programme milestones and selected innovators through different channels (such as project website, social media, newsletter, press releases, etc.).
- Participation to relevant external events and conferences.
- Organisation of joint hubs workshops and initiatives.

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ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
NGM	Next Generation Media
NGI	Next Generation Internet (Initiative)
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
OC1	Open Call 1
OC2	Open Call 2
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

Prepared in the context of Work Package 5 (WP5), this deliverable serves two major purposes:

- Report on the progress and key achievements of STADIEM's outreach and impact creation activities held from month 1 to month 18 (October 2020 to March 2022).
- Lay out a plan of outreach and impact creation activities for month 19 to month 36 (April 2022 to September 2023) to ensure the fulfilment of targets and supporting the successful conclusion of the project.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The sections of this deliverable are organised as follows: After the introductory **Section 1**, **Section 2** depicts outreach and impact creation activities and tools used during the first half of the project (M1-M18). **Section 3** outlines the outreach and impact creation actions to be carried out in the second half of the project (M19-M36), while **Section 4** focuses on the assessment of the activities' results. **Section 5** concludes the document, offering an overview on the next steps to be followed.

2 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION ACTIVITIES M1-M18

2.1 OBJECTIVES AND STAKEHOLDERS

STADIEM addresses three key pain points in the European media sector: (a) cross-border scalability; (b) start-up to corporate to market techtransfer, and (c) the availability of innovative media services in a Digital Single Market framework. As such, STADIEM's ambition is to contribute to identifying, nurturing, and retaining promising start-ups and connecting them with media industries by creating concrete opportunities to collaborate.

Outreach and impact creation activities are central to the overall STADIEM goal. They are being closely monitored and coordinated to ensure a broad visibility and an effective engagement of all targeted stakeholders in the Next Generation Media, including those from the media and non-media sectors (verticals). These activities are coordinated by Martel with active contributions from all STADIEM partners, following the objectives below:

- Ensure STADIEM's broad visibility by spreading knowledge about the project and its results, as well as establishing a distinctive and recognizable identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts.
- Reach a wide network of innovators interested in taking part in the STADIEM Open Calls (2).
- Reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that (a) the Open Calls and Incubation Programme of the project are effectively and properly disseminated to the targeted audiences for maximum participation and promotion, (b) the results of the project and third-party projects, selected through STADIEM Open Calls, are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement and possibly further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts.
- Facilitate exploitation of the project's outcomes and promote the development of innovative solutions based on the STADIEM methodology and concepts.
- To fully support the key players' engagement strategy in the project activities and concepts around the Open Calls and the Incubation Programme, while promoting and providing great visibility on the third-party projects and the best practices learned that will lead to the creation of (a) new business model(s) in the media domain.
- Establish strong liaisons and ensure close collaboration with relevant initiatives in the media industry.

2.2 ONLINE DISSEMINATION

2.2.1 Website

Launched at the beginning of the project (M2), the STADIEM website (<https://www.stadiem.eu>) has been developed to act as an information hub presenting the project's goals, activities, and achievements. To this purpose, content has been constantly updated and featured as follows:

- General information about the project, its vision and objectives
- Introduction of the consortium and Advisory Board members

- Information about both STADIEM Open Calls (dedicated info page and FAQs section) and opportunities for media tech innovators
- Portfolio of the scale-ups taking part in the STADIEM programme
- News items and press releases
- List of relevant events
- A repository of resources, such as publications, presentations/talks, promotional materials, videos, and public deliverables
- Contact information
- An acknowledgment and reference to relevant initiatives on Next Generation Media in Europe

The website is being periodically updated according to the progress of the project. Until today (end of March 2022), the website counts around 10,400 unique visitors, who generated around **22,900 page views** on an **average visit duration of 01'17"**. Drilling down into specific pages, the most popular pages - alongside the homepage – are the the Open Call pages, counting a total of 5,690 views.

The figures below provide the aforementioned plus some additional details: Figure 1 (Traffic overview and visit duration), Figure 2 (Top visited pages) and Figure 3 (Visits per country).

FIGURE 1: STADIEM WEBSITE - TRAFFIC OVERVIEW AND VISIT DURATION

Page	Page Views	Unique Page Views	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit
1. /open-call-2/	4,223 (16.94%)	3,788 (18.21%)	00:03:47	3,268 (21.08%)	85.74%	81.93%
2. /	2,332 (9.36%)	1,997 (9.60%)	00:01:12	1,831 (11.81%)	37.74%	38.25%
3. /open-call-1/	1,470 (5.90%)	1,316 (6.33%)	00:02:31	954 (6.15%)	78.20%	72.11%
4. /about/	493 (1.98%)	427 (2.05%)	00:01:42	145 (0.94%)	48.97%	36.71%
5. /faqs/	484 (1.94%)	411 (1.98%)	00:03:53	178 (1.15%)	75.28%	61.16%
6. /open-calls/	470 (1.89%)	402 (1.93%)	00:01:30	175 (1.13%)	53.71%	37.87%
7. /consortium/	345 (1.38%)	320 (1.54%)	00:01:20	81 (0.52%)	62.96%	38.26%
8. /how-stadiem-works/	258 (1.04%)	236 (1.13%)	00:01:47	59 (0.38%)	62.71%	37.21%
9. /news/	253 (1.02%)	216 (1.04%)	00:00:39	48 (0.31%)	45.83%	26.88%
10. /scaleups/	243 (0.97%)	201 (0.97%)	00:00:46	60 (0.39%)	20.00%	14.81%

FIGURE 2: STADIEM WEBSITE – TOP VISITED PAGES

Country	Users	% Users
1. Romania	1,025	9.83%
2. Bulgaria	696	6.67%
3. Cyprus	683	6.55%
4. Belgium	662	6.35%
5. Greece	592	5.68%
6. Germany	572	5.48%
7. Croatia	336	3.22%
8. United Kingdom	328	3.15%
9. Poland	302	2.90%
10. Portugal	295	2.83%

FIGURE 3: STADIEM WEBSITE – VISITS PER COUNTRY

All information and e-mails collected are protected under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Contact is and will continue to only be made with people who have submitted inquiries. Similarly, the newsletters are and will continue to be sent out only to individuals who have explicitly requested to receive them. Any person who has subscribed can request for their e-mail address to be removed from the list. The website provides information on the data kept and how they are used in alignment with the GDPR under the Privacy Policy link (footer of the webpage).

2.2.2 Social media channels

STADIEM established its presence on social media channels to regularly promote the project activities and output while encouraging a wider promotion of Next Generation Media solutions. The project has built a fair follower base on several social media channels, namely Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, which are all linked to the project's website.

2.2.2.1 Twitter

STADIEM uses Twitter as a social network to cover the news in real-time, cross-share relevant and interesting initiatives, and to establish meaningful connections with targeted groups of stakeholders, including policy makers, industry, and the general public. So far, the [STADIEM Twitter account](#) has reached **208 followers** (including project partners, similar projects, interested stakeholders, etc.). In total, around **367 tweets** have been posted. The project also follows 86 accounts, mostly projects and initiatives in similar fields or of approximate nature where partners have been involved. Over the duration of Open Call 2's promotion, the average engagement rate was 3,8% (with peaks reaching 23%) and the account registered over 19,000 total clicks.

FIGURE 4: STADIEM TWITTER ACCOUNT

2.2.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn allows the project to network with individuals and organizations within the media industry and beyond, share crucial information about project activities, and stay up to date on the latest developments in the field. [The LinkedIn account](#) has gathered **429 followers** so far. Similarly to Twitter, the LinkedIn account is mostly used to share the latest progress of STADIEM, echoing key promotional messages from the project website and sharing relevant news from the project's partners, pertinent projects and the European Commission. During the recent Open Call 2 promotion, the account reached a peak of 418 unique visitors, in an audience prevalently working in the fields of business development, entrepreneurship and media and communication.

FIGURE 5: STADIEM LINKEDIN ACCOUNT

2.2.2.3 YouTube

STADIEM has also created an [account on YouTube](#), one of the leading video-sharing platforms. This channel has been opened at the early project stages to disseminate the first project video. Since then, the project has released a total of **22 videos** on the channel. For more details on the channel's reach and content, please refer to section 2.3.1.

FIGURE 6: STADIEM YOUTUBE CHANNEL

2.2.3 News items and Newsletter

The STADIEM consortium keeps the community and the general public informed about key activities, undertakings, and events by regularly publishing news items and press releases. To date, **18 news items** have been published on the project website.

5 Newsletters - collecting such items, plus additional strategic communication - have been edited and distributed to stakeholders through STADIEM's mailing lists as well as made available on the project website. According to the outreach plan, the initial goal would have been to have 6 newsletters by M18, but a decision was taken to delay the 1st newsletter, to have it coincide with the launch of OC1; therefore, an additional newsletter/newsflash will be released in the second half of the project. So far, **281 stakeholders** have subscribed to receive STADIEM's newsletter. In terms of further analysis on the efficiency of the communication:

- ➡ The 1st newsletter (February 2021) was sent to 58 subscribers / 87% opens / 24% clicks
- ➡ The 2nd newsletter (May 2021) was sent to 224 subscribers / 58% opens / 21% clicks
- ➡ The 3rd newsletter (September 2021) was sent out to 246 subscribers / 55% opens / 15% clicks
- ➡ The 4th newsletter (December 2021) was sent out to 265 subscribers / 58% opens / 17% clicks
- ➡ The 5th newsletter (February 2022) was sent out to 276 subscribers / 54% opens / 12% clicks

1) Newsletter 1 (February 2021)

The 1st newsletter of STADIEM, published in February 2021, informed stakeholders on the project's kick-off, presented consortium members and promoted Open Call 1's application (and the related 1st info webinar).

FIGURE 7: SCREENSHOT OF STADIEM'S NEWSLETTER 1

2) Newsletter 2 (May 2021)

The 2nd newsletter of STADIEM, published in May 2021, presented the insights of the Open Call 1 applications and introduced the start-ups selected for the match phase. Updates about several EU policy and funding initiatives were provided.

FIGURE 8: SCREENSHOT OF STADIEM'S NEWSLETTER 2

3) Newsletter 3 (September 2021)

The 3rd newsletter of STADIEM, published in September 2021, featured the takeaways from start-ups following OC1's match phase and introduced the 16 scale-ups going to the second phase of the STADIEM programme.

FIGURE 9: SCREENSHOT OF STADIEM'S NEWSLETTER 3

4) Newsletter 4 (December 2021)

The 4th newsletter of STADIEM, published in December 2021, informed stakeholders about the opening of the Open Call 2's application round. In addition, this issue promoted the videos of the four STADIEM Hubs giving their take on the programme and provided the highlights of the events attended by the consortium.

FIGURE 10: SCREENSHOT OF STADIEM'S NEWSLETTER 4

5) Newsletter 5 (February 2022)

The 5th newsletter of STADIEM, published in February 2022, continued the advertising of Open Call 2 focusing on the info webinars promotion and the takeaways from the Open Call 1's scale-ups.

FIGURE 11: SCREENSHOT OF STADIEM'S NEWSLETTER 5

2.3 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic on in-person events, all plans for printed material (as detailed in section 4) such as posters, roll-ups and flyers, stickers and booth elements had to be kept on hold. WP5 and the project consortium therefore agreed on rather shifting efforts towards

digital alternatives, namely strategic advertising social media campaigns (see section 2.6, in connection to the Open Calls) and videos.

2.3.1 Videos

In the first reporting period STADIEM released **22 videos** which have been uploaded on the STADIEM YouTube channel and mirrored on STADIEM's website. So far, the project's YouTube Channel reached a total of **1,879 views**. Although some of the videos were specifically conceived to support the Open Calls (both in terms of advertising and guidance for potential applicants), most of the videos also allowed to promote the project's incubation and acceleration programme.

- The video "Meet the teams of the NMA Batch 11!", is a brief explainer video informing stakeholders about the start-ups involved in partner's NMA Batch 11, serving as an overview on the type of media-related solutions and ecosystem they have been involved with. The video was published in December 2020.

FIGURE 12: SCREENSHOT FROM "MEET THE TEAMS OF THE NMA BATCH 11!"

- The video "STADIEM – Piloting and acceleration programme" is a brief overview video informing stakeholders (namely potential Open Calls applicants) about the project's programme and funding opportunities. The video was created at VRT's facilities and originally published on Twitter in March 2021 as part of OC1's promotion. The video was subsequently re-released on STADIEM's YouTube channel in November 2021 to be used as part of OC2's promotion as well.

FIGURE 13: SCREENSHOT FROM "STADIEM – PILOTING AND ACCELERATION PROGRAMME"

- An animated 20-second video ad was created to promote OC1's info webinars: the clip was also deployed on Twitter and LinkedIn and used as part of OC1's paid Adv campaign (see section 2.6.1 for details). The video was first released in February 2021.

FIGURE 14: SCREENSHOT FROM THE OC1 INFO WEBINARS VIDEO AD

- The full-length video recordings of the OC1 info webinars presented the call's objectives, phases and application tips, closing with a Q&A with the participants. The videos were published in February and March 2021 as support material for potential applicants.

FIGURE 15: SCREENSHOT FROM THE RECORDING OF OC1'S INFO WEBINAR #1

- The video "STADIEM's First Consortium Meeting and Pitching Event @ Future Week" is a brief video reportage covering the very first in-person consortium meeting in Bergen (Norway), at MCB's headquarters, where the partners also met some of OC1's scale-ups taking part in the pitching event organised within Future Week. The video was filmed on location and published in October 2021.

FIGURE 16: SCREENSHOT FROM "STADIEM'S FIRST CONSORTIUM MEETING AND PITCHING EVENT @ FUTURE WEEK"

- The video series "The Hubs on Open Call 1" is a series of brief testimonials from representatives of STADIEM's hubs, expressing their take on the success of the programme and talking about some of the solutions they worked with. The video was created with the double scope of promoting the ongoing project's activities and solutions fostered, whilst offering a taste of the programme's advantages and opportunities to potential OC2 applicants. Also filmed on location during the consortium meeting in Bergen, the series was released periodically, from early November 2021 to mid-December 2021, as a teaser campaign for OC2's opening.

FIGURE 17: PREVIEW SCREEN FOR THE "THE HUBS ON OPEN CALL 1" SERIES, AS PRESENTED IN NEWSLETTER #4

- The video "EU funding for 40 B2B start-ups in MediaTech: STADIEM at SLUSH" is a full recording of the eponymous event organised by the consortium in the context of SLUSH on 1st December 2021 in Helsinki (Finland) - More information on the event can be found in section 2.5.1 of this document. Filmed on location, the video was released shortly after OC2's opening, in early December 2021.

FIGURE 18: SCREENSHOT FROM “EU-FUNDING FOR 40 B2B START-UPS IN MEDIATECH: STADIEM AT SLUSH”

- The video “STADIEM at MCB Expo” is a recording of the playful presentation held by Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT) as part of part of MCB Expo, a hybrid event taking place in Bergen, Oslo and online on 3rd December 2021, presenting all the new solutions, projects, products, and iterations that were supposed to be launched during the cancelled IBC 2021 in Amsterdam.

FIGURE 19: SCREENSHOT FROM “STADIEM AT MCB EXPO”

- The video series “The Scale-ups on Open Call 1” is a series of brief testimonials from eight of the scale-ups then involved in OC1’s develop phase, expressing their take on the programme, talking about the matches they’ve made and the solutions they consequently started collaborating on. The videos were collected remotely after the cancellation of IBC 2021 (which was intended as the original filming location) and released in the period from mid-January to the beginning of March 2022, thus overlapping with the ongoing Open Call 2 and joining its promotional campaign - while still offering a platform to showcase the innovators from the first cohort.

FIGURE 20: PREVIEW SCREEN FOR THE "THE SCALE-UPS ON OPEN CALL 1" SERIES, AS PRESENTED IN NEWSLETTER #5

- The full-length video recordings of the OC2 info webinars presented the call's objectives, phases and application tips, closing with a Q&A with the participants. The videos were published in January and February 2021 as support material for potential applicants.

FIGURE 21: SCREENSHOT FROM THE RECORDING OF OC2'S INFO WEBINAR #1

2.4 PRESS RELEASES AND PRESS COVERAGE

To date, **6 press releases** have been issued by STADIEM, matching with key moments such as the launch of both Open Calls and announcements related to the selection phases of the project's piloting and acceleration programme. All press releases were made available on the [dedicated section of the project's website](#). The 4th and 5th press releases (issued in September and December 2021) were also respectively **distributed to 30 and 150 contacts in the specialized press** through [Prowly](#); the 5th press release being specifically designed to promote the launch of the Open Call 2. Along these set parameters, a 6th release followed in March 2022, informing on the beginning of the Integrate phase of Open Call 1 and initiating a call to corporates to join the programme for Open Call 2.

In the table below, we detail the relevant press coverage obtained by the project – The articles mentioned have been made available in the ["Publications & Press clipping"](#) section of STADIEM's website – A selection of press clipping is also present as an annex to this document.

TABLE 1 : STADIEM PRESS COVERAGE IN THE FIRST HALF OF THE PROJECT

PUBLICATION	URL	LEAD PARTNER
VRT Innovatie (OC1 promotion)	https://innovatie.vrt.be/en/artikel/en/sign-up-for-STADIEM-and-fund-your-media-solution	VRT
VRT Innovatie (OC1 promotion)	https://innovatie.vrt.be/event/stadiem-open-call-1	VRT
VRT Website (Updates on OC1's scale-ups)	https://www.vrt.be/nl/over-de-vrt/nieuws/2021/08/31/vrt-brengt-europese-top-scale-ups-naar-vlaanderen-om-samen-te-in/	VRT
VRT Website (OC2 promotion)	https://www.vrt.be/nl/over-de-vrt/nieuws/2021/12/15/stadiem-doet-openoproep-aan-start-ups-en-scale-ups/	VRT
VRT Innovatie (OC2 promotion)	https://innovatie.vrt.be/en/artikel/en/1-93-million-euro-for-European-start-ups-and-scale-ups-to-work-on-Next-Generation-Media-solutions	VRT
tech-i magazine - issue 50: "Testing what's possible with 5G-based production"	https://tech.ebu.ch/publications/tech-i-050 (also published separately at: https://tech.ebu.ch/news/2021/12/stadiem-calling-innovators-to-enhance-europes-next-generation-media-ecosystem)	EBU

2.5 EVENTS

2.5.1 STADIEM workshops and webinars

2.5.1.1 Joint hubs workshops

The aim of these workshops is to address the different categories of stakeholders (detailed in the Outreach and Impact Creation Strategy and Plan D5.x): traditional media operators, media producers, technologists and technology innovators, start-ups, scale-ups, business incubators and accelerators. The objective is to match the needs of the media sector with innovative solutions sustained by appropriate funding opportunities.

Although the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic reduced in-person events and chances of co-location with larger events, **1 workshop** was organised during the first part of the project, taking place physically instead of in the virtual format originally expected. The event, entitled "**EU funding for 40 B2B start-ups in MediaTech**", was delayed to M15 to be held as a side

event of [SLUSH](#) (one of the world's leading start-up events) in Helsinki, on 1st December 2021. It was jointly run by STADIEM's partners Storytek/The Exit Academy. It was connected to a designated workshop by VRT (Future Media Hubs), and the associated project [Media Motor Europe](#). Aimed at B2B investors (and founders), the event focused on tips to improve their portfolio, introduced the top start-ups/scale-ups from STADIEM's Open Call 1 and announced the project's upcoming Open Call 2. The attendance counted **75 people and had over 100 in the waiting list** (due to room size the event was at full capacity), attracting a varied crowd with access to investors or connections in the media industry. The speakers of the event were Sten Saluveer and Heikki Haldre from Storytek/The Exit Academy, Jevgeni Kabanov, the CTO of Europe's leading unicorn Bolt, and, as mentioned in section 2.3.1, the event's full recording was released on STADIEM's website and promoted on social media.

FIGURE 22: SOCIAL MEDIA CARD AND SNAPSHOT FROM THE "EU-FUNDING FOR 40 B2B START-UPS IN MEDIATECH

2.5.1.2 Open Calls webinars

In line with what anticipated in Section 4.3 of D5.2, **STADIEM organised 4 info webinars** presenting to launch and present the Open Calls. The webinars were promoted across the stakeholders identified under Task 1.1 (Community Building Strategy and community management) through the online communication channels, and with the support of 2 advertising campaigns (see section 2.6). The scope of the webinars was to inform innovative start-ups/scale-ups of the objectives and conditions of participation to the STADIEM Open Calls.

The two **OC1 webinars** (held on 22nd February and 10th March 2021) reached **90 and 70 participants**, while the two **OC2 webinars** (held on 28th January and 10th February 2022) reached **45 and 36 participants**. As detailed in Section 2.3.1, all webinars were recorded and made available through STADIEM's YouTube channel and website (both in the OCs info pages and in the "Videos" section) – The release of the recordings was also promoted via social media.

FIGURE 23: SCREENSHOT FROM OC2 INFO WEBINAR 2

2.5.2 Events attended

STADIEM's partners have attended or participated to **33 events** so far, giving keynote presentations and promoting the projects goals and achievements, and the Open Calls. The table here below summarizes the events attended. These participations have been reported in the news section and the events calendar of the project's website and have been promoted through the social media channels and newsletters.

TABLE 2 : EVENTS ATTENDED M1-M18

EVENT	DATE, LOCATION	TYPE OF AUDIENCE	APPROX. AUDIENCE SIZE	ACTIVITIES	LEAD PARTNER
Berlinale EFM & EFM Startups 2021	1-5 March 2021, Online	Decision-makers, start-ups, corporates	50	Discussant in panel, one-to-one meetings for matchmaking	Storytek
SXSW 2021	11-20 March 2021, Online	Start-ups, VCs, corporates	10,000	Matchmaking, networking	Storytek
FANDANGO Project's "Rethinking the possibilities of data and technology in the fight against disinformation"	26 March 2021, Online	Researchers, policy-makers, media industry	100	Presentation in panel	VRT
Collision Conf 2021	20 - 22 April 2021, Online	Start-ups, VCs, corporates	10,000	Matchmaking, networking	Storytek
Creative FLIP policy forum	18 May 2021, Online	Policy-makers	50	Presenter, discussant, communication of impact	Storytek
Virtual Media Match	20 May 2021, Online	Media Industry, start-ups, investors	120	Panel discussion, possibility for matchmaking	NMA

Future Peak	11,18, 25 June + 2 July 2021, Bergen (Norway)	Start-ups, scale-ups, corporates	60	Pitching, matchmaking, networking	MCB
Latitude59 2021	18 June 2021, Tallinn (Estonia) and Online	Start-ups, investors	500	Networking, matchmaking	Storytek
Mediatech on Stage	22 June 2021, Online	Start-ups, corporates, investors	100 - 200	Pitching, matchmaking, networking	VRT, MCB
Kinnernet Europe 2021	23 - 25 June 2021, Online	Start-ups, VCs, corporates	50	Matchmaking, networking	Storytek
Sandbox Hub Pitch	5 July 2021, Online	Media industry	21	Pitching event for Sandbox Hub, prior to STADIEM Match phase	VRT
Marche Du Film - Festival de Cannes	7 - 18 July 2021, Cannes (France)	Media industry, start-ups, corporates	7,500	Networking, matchmaking, promotion of project	Storytek
Sport 1	9 July 2021, Online	Start-ups, scale-ups, Sport 1 management	12	Pitching, matchmaking, networking	NMA
RTL	11 July 2021, Online	Start-ups, scale-ups, RTL management	14	Pitching, matchmaking, networking	NMA
sSTARTUp Day 2021	25 - 27 August 2021, Tartu (Estonia)	Start-ups, VCs, corporates	3,000	Networking, matchmaking, promotion of project	Storytek
Venice Market	4 - 11 September 2021, Venice (Italy)	XR start-ups, decision-makers	10,000	Research and networking	Storytek

FDCP Summit	16 - 19 September 2021, Online	Start-ups and scale-ups in the film industry, corporates	135	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Future Week	27 September - 1 October 2021, Bergen, (Norway) and Online	Data journalists, coders, developers, leaders, designers, techologists, students, scientists	80	Networking, STADIEM Pitch Contest, stakeholder engagement	MCB
NMA Demo Day	12 October 2021, Hamburg, (Germany) and online	Media Industry, start-ups	Approx. 30 on site, approx. 100 online	Stakeholders engagement	NMA
Arttech 2021	13 - 15 October 2021, Portugal	Start-ups, scale-ups, corporates	100	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
B3 Biennale Market 2021	16 - 20 October 2021, Frankfurt am Main (Germany) and Online	Start-ups	30	Mentoring, matchmaking, networking	Storytek
Geneva Digital Market	7 - 10 November 2021, Geneva (Switzerland)	Start-ups, media corporates	150	Matchmaking, one-to-one meetings	Storytek
Sandbox Hub Challenges	8 November 2021, Online	Media industry, start-ups, scale-ups	5 Media houses + 5 Scale-ups	Pitching event, stakeholder engagement	VRT
Infrachain Summit	18 November 2021, Luxembourg/ Italy and Online	Creative industries, technologists, start-ups, scale-ups	100	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek

Industry@Tallinn & Baltic Event	22-26 November, 2021, Tallinn (Estonia)	Decision-makers, corporates	1,500	One-to-one meetings, networking, matchmaking	Storytek
Sandbox Hub Challenges	30 November 2021, Online	Media industry, start-ups, scale-ups	5 Media houses + 5 Scale-ups	Pitching event, stakeholder engagement	VRT
Slush	1 - 2 December 2021, Helsinki	Investors, start-ups, scale-ups, corporates	75	Networking, presentations, workshop, stakeholder engagement	Storytek
MCB Expo	3 December 2021, Bergen/Oslo, Norway and Online	Corporates, industry, start-ups, scale-ups	100	Presentation, stakeholders engagement	MCB, VRT
Wallifornia Pitch of International Start-ups	6 December 2021, Online	Start-ups, scale-ups	14 Attendees + 8 Start-ups	Pitching event	VRT
EBU PTS 2022	1 - 3 February 2022, Geneva, Switzerland and Online	Media industry, broadcasters	>500	Presentation	NMA
Berlinale & EFM Startups 2022	10-15 February 2022, Berlin (Germany)	Decision-makers, start-ups, corporates	1,000	Promotion of results of OC1 and call for OC2	Storytek
Kinnernord 2022	17 - 20 March 2022	Investors, start-ups	75	Matchmaking, networking, "Future of Media" presentation session	Storytek
SXSW 2022	10-20 March 2022, Online	Decision-makers, start-ups, corporates	10,000	Promotion of results of OC1 and call for OC2	Storytek

2.6 PROMOTION OF OPEN CALLS

The promotion of STADIEM's Open Calls was one of WP5 key efforts, coordinated by Martel with the cooperation of all partners and STADIEM Advisory Board. The Open Calls have been promoted across all STADIEM's communication channels (website, newsletter, social media), consortium partners' social media outlets and networks, and presented at several events, whenever possible. Paid advertising campaigns were planned for both Open Calls to boost awareness, functioning as a valid alternative to compensate the lack of in-person promotional platforms caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The communication was also extended to media not owned by STADIEM and its partners, reaching targeted stakeholders, with a focus on start-ups/scale-ups. Such channels include several relevant initiatives on Next Generation Media in Europe and beyond, as well as other main liaison projects, in particular:

- [Media Motor Europe](#) and [Möbius](#) projects (newsletter and social media);
- [NGI](#) initiative and [NGI Explorers](#) (newsletter, Comm Task Force Mailing list and LinkedIn group);
- [BDVA](#) newsletter;
- [5G PPP](#) initiative's Comm mailing list and selected contacts in the [FLAME project](#)'s network, and in the [Fed4Fire+](#) mailing list;
- the [European Commission portal](#) for competitive calls and calls for third parties.

A dedicated one-to-one mailing has been additionally directed to the National Contact Points (NCP) for the ICT and Future and Emerging Technologies programmes: 186 people have been contacted representing all EC Member States and Third Countries (for some countries, multiple contact points).

More details on the estimated reach will be offered in sub-sections 2.6.1 and 2.6.2.

2.6.1 Open Call 1

For Open Call 1 (running from 1st February to 31st March 2021) in addition to the social media countdown campaign detailed in section 4.7.1 of [D5.2](#), Martel's creative team developed a range of communication assets - namely social media copy, cards and 2 brief video ads, one of which exclusively used on social media - dedicated to promote the call and the two connected info webinars (Figures 24, 25 and 26).

FIGURE 24: STADIEM OC1 SOCIAL MEDIA CARD

FIGURE 25: SCREENSHOT FROM THE OC1 WEBINARS VIDEO AD

FIGURE 26: SCREENSHOT FROM THE OC1 SOCIAL MEDIA VIDEO AD

The assets were deployed through several channels upon the OC1’s opening and throughout its run, as detailed in Figure 27, which also provides the estimated reach. The shared info webinar recordings, live tweeting during the info webinars and the re-sharing of the “STADIEM Piloting and Acceleration Programme” video overview also created traction.

FIGURE 27: OC1 PROMOTION – CHANNELS, ASSETS AND REACH

As shown in Figure 27, the paid advertising campaign had a consistent reach and was deployed on three different platforms (mostly using the video ads produced) in two rounds: before the 1st OC1 webinar and towards the end of the call’s run. The Table below offers additional details on the threefold campaign and its targeting:

TABLE 3 : OC1 PAID ADV CAMPAIGN IN DETAIL

PLATFORM	BUDGET	DURATION	LOCATION	KEYWORDS/TARGETING
Google Ads	€225	15-22 February 2021	EU countries	Start-up, funding, media, SME, H2020, incubation, acceleration, scale-up
Twitter Ads	€259,89	15-23 February 2021	EU countries	Start-up, funding, media, SME, H2020, incubation, acceleration, scale-up Followers and similar/relevant accounts
LinkedIn Ads	€372,67	15-23 March 2021	Europe	Start-up, funding, media, SME, H2020, incubation, acceleration, scale-up Media Production

2.6.2 Open Call 2

For Open Call 2 (running from 15th December 2021 to 28th February 2022), WP5 opted for a similar overall strategy, maintaining some successfully applied aspects while adding a degree of fine-tuning, based on the post-OC1 communication analysis conducted by VRT and Martel and input from F6S, the rest of the consortium and the Advisory Board (the main occasion to bring all feedback together consisting in the in-person consortium meeting held in Bergen, Norway in September 2022).

The promotion of OC 2 started in early December 2021 with an official announcement launched at SLUSH 2021. To create more awareness on the themes and advantages of the STADIEM programme a greater variety in content (visuals and text) and start-ups' testimonials were introduced in the promotional assets. Communication was directed on the programme's focus areas (Figure 28) and the success stories from the OC 1's start-ups/scale-ups were featured in the video testimonials mentioned in section 2.3.1; the OC2 campaign assets added focus to timeframe/deadline and correct application process (Figure 29) to the video ads and static cards solely focused on promoting the info webinars (Figure 30).

FIGURE 28: SOCIAL MEDIA CARD FROM THE "STADIEM FOCUS AREAS" CAMPAIGN

FIGURE 29: OC2 SOCIAL MEDIA CARDS

FIGURE 30: SCREENSHOT FROM THE OC2 WEBINARS VIDEO AD AND STATIC PROMOTIONAL CARD

Figure 31, here below, details how aforementioned assets were deployed, and the estimated reach obtained, the data including OC2’s adv campaign as well.

FIGURE 31: OC2 PROMOTION – CHANNELS, ASSETS AND REACH

For OC2, the paid advertising campaign was deployed only on two platforms, excluding LinkedIn (as the balance between costs and performance proved less satisfactory during OC1), while covering a double timeframe right before both OC2 info webinars. Based on the results of the OC1 paid advertising campaign and to reach a wider and more interested network of innovators, the OC2 campaign adjusted its targeting features by focusing on selecting and monitoring keywords, interests, and demographics. Additional details can be found in the Table below.

TABLE 4 : OC2 PAID ADV CAMPAIGN IN DETAIL

PLATFORM	BUDGET	DURATION	LOCATION	KEYWORDS/TARGETING
Google Ads	€372	19 – 27 January and 2 – 10 February 2022	EU countries	Start-up, scale-up, SME, media, incubation, acceleration, media innovation, funding, H2020 Focus areas keywords
Twitter Ads	€359,98	19 – 27 January and 2 – 10 February 2022	EU countries	Start-up, scale-up, SME, media, incubation, acceleration, media innovation, funding, H2020 Focus areas keywords Followers and similar/relevant accounts

3 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION PLAN M19-M36

STADIEM's dissemination and communication plan will continue to be coordinated by Martel, Task 5.1 leader, with the contribution and support of all partners. The planned activities include participation and organization of events.

3.1 PLANNED WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

STADIEM envisages to organize the remaining planned 3 joint hubs workshops by the end of the project, with possible shifts in timeline depending on the pursuit of co-location with major events (Cannes and SLUSH have been proposed by the partners, for instance) and coordination with other NGM-connected projects and related national and international initiatives, to maximize impact and attendance. The envisioned timeline is as follows (revised following the impact of COVID-19 and the shift of the 1st workshop):

- The second workshop is now planned to match the end of OC1's Pilot phase (M23), to discuss its outcomes with relevant stakeholders.
- The third workshop is now planned for M28 as an update on OC2's Develop phase.
- The fourth workshop remains planned to match the conclusion of OC2's Pilot phase (M36) and combination with the Final Demo Day (described here below) is being considered.

Not underestimating the possibility of new travel restrictions, we will keep in mind alternative solutions for live streaming and recording of these events (e.g., YouTube Live), to reach a remote audience and make the projects' outputs as widely available as possible.

➔ Final project Demo Day

As anticipated in D5.2, a Final Demo Day is planned for M36, with the objective to showcase the resulting products developed and piloted by funded start-ups/scale-ups under the two STADIEM open calls. A decision on the format, location of the event and/or possible colocation with a bigger event is planned to be made at the beginning of Year 3.

3.2 PLANNED EVENTS PARTICIPATION

The table below presents a list of events for which participation in the second half of the project has been planned, or that will be in STADIEM's radar for communication and dissemination activities:

TABLE 5 : EVENTS PARTICIPATION PLANNED FOR M19-M36

EVENT	DATE, LOCATION	TYPE OF AUDIENCE	APPROX. AUDIENCE SIZE	ACTIVITIES	LEAD PARTNER
EU Startups Summit 2022	12-13 May 2022,	Start-ups corporates, investors,	1,500	Stakeholder engagement	TBD

	Barcelona (Spain)	and Media industry			
(OMR) Online Marketing Rockstars	17-18 May, Hamburg (Germany)	Start-ups, corporates, investors, media and marketing industry	55,000	Pitching	NMA
Latitude59	19-20 May 2022, Tallinn (Estonia) and Online	Investors, start-ups	5,000	Presentations, stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Cannes NEXT Media Innovation Platform (Cannes Marché Du Film)	17-25 May 2022, Cannes (France)	Corporates, media industry	10,000	Presentations, stakeholder engagement	Storytek
DLD Munich	20-22 May 2022, Munich (Germany)	Investors, corporates	5,000	Stakeholder engagement	Storytek
MDN 2022	31 May – 2 June 2022, online	Start-ups, corporates, researchers	100	Meetings, networking, presentations	EBU
MediaTech Festival 2022	1-3 June 2022, Odense (Denmark)	Investors, start-ups, corporates	500	Stakeholder engagement	TBD
Future Week	7-10 June 2022, Bergen (Norway)	Start-ups corporates, investors, and media industry	1,000	Presentations, stakeholder engagement, networking	MCB
Arctic15	15 June 2022, Helsinki (Finland)	Investors, start-ups, corporates	3,000	Meetings, networking, presentations	Storytek
Kinnernet Europe Conference	23 -25 June 2022, Avallon, (France)	Investors, start-ups, corporates	125	Meetings, networking, presentations	Storytek

Collision 2022	20-23 June, Toronto (Canada) and Online	Investors, start-ups, corporates	10,000	Meetings, networking, presentations	Storytek
Webit Impact Forum	28-29 June 2022, Sofia (Bulgaria) and online	Investors, start-ups, corporates	15,000	Stakeholder engagement	Storytek
ICDBIT 2022: Digital Broadcasting and Interactive Television Conference	21-22 July 2022, Berlin (Germany)	Media industry professionals, researchers, academics	250	Presentations, workshops	TBD
sSTARTUp Day	24-26 August 2022, Tartu (Estonia) and online	Investors, start-ups, corporates	5,000	Presentations, stakeholder engagement	Storytek
DLD Tel Aviv	September 2022, Tel Aviv (Israel)	Investors, start-ups, corporates	5,000	Presentations, stakeholder engagement	Storytek
IBC 2022	9-12 September 2022, Amsterdam (the Netherlands)	Start-ups corporates, investors, and media industry	55,000	Demo, presentations, stakeholder engagement, networking	MCB
FIWARE Global Summit Gran Canaria 2022	14-15 September 2022, Gran Canaria (Spain)	Corporates, researchers, academics	1,000	Stakeholder engagement	TBD
Geneva Digital Market	November 2022, Geneva (Switzerland)	Start-ups corporates, investors, and media industry	150	Demo, presentations, stakeholder engagement, networking	Storytek
Slush	17-18 November 2022, Helsinki (Finland)	Investors, start-ups, corporates	20,000	Networking, presentations, stakeholder engagement	Storytek

3.3 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

3.3.1 Online Communication

Continuous work will be dedicated to the online presence, populating and keeping STADIEM's website updated. The social media will continue to be animated with the project's and partners' news and sharing relevant contents of the EC and other initiatives in the NGM and H2020 ecosystems. Extensive coverage will continue to be dedicated to Open Call 1 and 2: both on the progress of the respective programmes and on the start-ups/scale-ups involved in the selection rounds and phases.

In order to strengthen the collaboration between media industry organisations and start-ups, a communication campaign targeting media corporates (such as broadcasters, film distributors, publishers, record labels) will be implemented. To this end, a promotional kit aimed at corporates, created in M18, will be at the consortium's disposal to be used throughout M19 to approach potential new corporates for the upcoming OC2's match phase.

3.3.2 Promotional materials

WP5 and the STADIEM consortium continue to keep the creation of printed material under consideration for future in-person events. Some assets were in fact already prepared for the cancelled IBC 2021 and can be reused for participation in the 2022 edition.

3.3.3 Videos

Although well above the planned video KPIs, with the major promotional efforts dedicated to the Open Calls now concluded, WP5 and the consortium consider continuing the successfully established video testimonials format, either dedicated to the upcoming phases of OC1's programme or focused on OC2's programme participants. Depending on the feasibility of in-person events in the immediate future, this and additional coverage and interviews could be conducted on location.

4 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION IMPACT ASSESSMENT

4.1 KPIS

The consortium has kept a close eye on the KPIs set at the beginning of the project, to monitor the Dissemination & Communication Results. The table below offers details on the currently achieved and planned KPIs.

TABLE 6 : STADIEM DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION KPIS

MEASURE	INDICATORS	KPI	MEANS OF VERIFICATION	ACHIEVED AT M18
Flyers, Posters, Roll-ups	N° of flyers N° of posters/roll-ups (by the end of the project)	> 6 > 4	Report of activities by partners	On hold due to cancellation of in-person events
Project website	Unique visitors per month (average per year)	> 1,500	Built-in website statistics tool	Online at M02 10,400 since inception
Social networks	N° of followers on Twitter, N° of followers on LinkedIn (average of new followers yearly)	> 300 > 100	Built-in platform analytics tool	208 Followers Twitter 429 Followers LinkedIn
e-Newsletter (every 3 months)	N° of newsletters (by the end of the project)	12	Publication on website	5
Videos	N° of videos published on the STADIEM website and social media and average n° of views	4 (videos per year), 100 views per video	YouTube analytics (+Twitter/LinkedIn Analytics)	22 Videos Tot. views YT: 1,879 Twitter+LinkedIn: >300k impressions

Workshops - at least 4 by the end of the project	Average n° of participants per workshop	Between 80 and 100	Registration and attendance lists, reports, presentations	1 workshop with 75 participants
Participation to events and presentations	N° of external events partners attended to promote the project	At least 6 per year	Reports, recording, presentations	33
Webinars (4 by the project end, 2 per OC)	Average n° of participants	At least 50	Registration and attendance lists, recording, reports, presentations	2 (OC1) 90+70 participants 2 (OC2) 45+36 participants
One open final event - Demo Day	Average n° of participants	200	Registration and attendance lists, recording, reports, presentations	n.a

5 CONCLUSIONS

Despite a challenging situation caused by various pandemic-related restrictions, the dissemination, communication and community building activities have been conducted in line with the previously outlined strategy and the project consortium is satisfied with the results consequently reached:

- The Open Calls' stakeholder engagement, and number of submissions, reached good numbers despite the lack of in-person events to be used as promotional platform.
- WP5 established a successful and proficient collaboration with partners and start-ups/scale-ups to produce communication materials remotely, as indicated by the large output.
- STADIEM managed to create a boosted communication and dissemination network thanks to the additional involvement of the start-ups/scale-ups present in the programme, leveraging on their own social media activity and network.
- The analysis of Open Call 1's promotion revealed the need for more focus on identified interest areas, additional countries, and tips for applications, which prompted a successful adjustment of website, promotional material and channel use, as well as deployment strategy for Open Call 2.

The communication, dissemination and community building activities will continue in the upcoming months, ensuring the successful conclusion of the project and maximising the benefit for its stakeholders. As key goals for the second half of the project, we aim to:

- Achieve a greater in-person events participation, which will be pursued, whenever feasible, as capital to build awareness on the project (and the European NGM ecosystem that it sets to enhance) and to give the involved start-ups/scale-ups greater chances to expand their network.
- Renew the efforts dedicated to the organisation of the missing planned workshops and of the Demo Day, adding to the venues to showcase the innovative solutions fostered by STADIEM's programme.
- Continue the video testimonial format used during the first half of the project, to promote the solutions of the start-ups/scale-ups involved in both OC1 and OC2's programmes.
- Keep the website updated with the profiles of the start-ups/scale-ups, offering more in-depth information on their innovation and the partnerships they've established during the programme.

ANNEX A – PRESS CLIPPING SELECTION

EUROPEAN PROJECTS

STADIEM: calling innovators to enhance Europe’s next-generation media ecosystem

In taking the lead on ecosystem engagement for the STADIEM project, the EBU has a capital role in the creation of a dynamic, innovation-focused community, writes **Carmela Asero** (EBU).

Running from 2017 to 2019, the EU-funded MediaRoad project boosted the development of a nurturing ecosystem for media innovation in Europe. Building on the experience of leading that project, the EBU is now part of STADIEM (stadiem.eu), another Horizon 2020 project, which kicked off in October 2020. STADIEM offers a competitive acceleration and co-creation programme bringing start-ups, scale-ups, investors and media organizations together to foster the development of next-generation media solutions.

START-UPS & SCALE-UPS

Throughout its four-stage programme of matching, developing, integrating and piloting, STADIEM provides start-ups and scale-ups with relevant skills, information and knowledge (including market and consumer specifics), insights into available funding and scaling opportunities, as well as connections with corporate networks. The EBU’s role is to lead the task of ecosystem engagement. This involves engaging with stakeholders across Europe to connect promising start-ups/scale-ups active in the media sector with a large network of established public service media organizations interested in adopting and deploying their products and solutions.

Alongside the EBU, the project consortium involves six other partners: EBU Member **VRT**, the coordinating partner; **Media City Bergen** (MCB), a leading international hub for media and technology innovation; **Next Media Accelerator** (NMA), which leads a pan-European start-up programme for innovation in media; **Storytek**, an accelerator and creative innovation hub with

deep audiovisual sector knowledge; **F6S**, the world’s largest community for tech founders and growth companies; and **Martel**, an SME with over 20 years of experience in managing research and innovation projects and their communication.

The acceleration and co-creation framework consisting of the four partner hubs (VRT, MCB, NMA and Storytek) aims to give the selected start-ups/scale-ups the best possible support in Europe in upscaling. The current batch of 16 start-ups/scale-ups that are co-creating media solutions with their corporate partner covers a range of relevant and challenging topics. The majority work on topics related to *data, AI, machine learning and synthetic media* (Ceretai, Smartocto, Web64, aiconix.ai, Datavillage, Utelly, Trensition, FanSifter, Visualyst) or *content creation and distribution* (Cutnut, On-Hertz, Framerright, Tinkerlist.tv). The others are developing solutions on *archiving* (The Chainless) and *monetization* (Nowtilus, FilmChain).

A FEW EXAMPLES

Here are three examples of partnerships being supported through STADIEM:

- With VRT, Ceretai is working on

a platform that automatically analyses diversity in audiovisual content. By measuring diversity and equality in a transparent way, media organizations can take informed decisions and strengthen an inclusive and equal media offering. Ceretai is also in discussions on a possible collaboration with the EBU’s diversity, equity and inclusion team.

- In making more content accessible to a wider audience, the use of language dialects becomes a barrier. In collaboration with Russmedia (Austria), aiconix.ai aims to improve dialect recognition for content creators, to support them in better transcription, subtitling and translation.
- The Chainless uses AI to recognize faces, scenes, segments and texts very accurately. They are working with ProSiebenSat.1 (Germany) on classifying and archiving audiovisual content, which, as a result, can be automatically tagged and personalized for the end user.

STADIEM’s second open call is scheduled for publication in December 2021. Follow the project’s social media channels to stay updated: stadiem.eu/contact/

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STADIEM IN TECH-I MAGAZINE (DECEMBER 2021)

1,93 million euro for European start-ups and scale-ups to work on Next Generation Media solutions

–DECEMBER 2021

The European STADIEM project, funded through Horizon 2020, officially launches its 2nd open call. Via the STADIEM piloting programme, start-ups and scale-ups can co-create solutions together with European media organisations, based on the sector's needs and challenges. The call provides access to funding, partners, and know-how for the development of Next Generation Media.

Already more than 400 start-ups and scale-ups in the European media sector were engaged with STADIEM's 1st open call, leading to over 200 applications and 40 selected proposals. Currently, 16 scale-ups are working together with European media organisations (including VRT, Roularta Media Group, Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung, Marathon Music Group and several others) to tackle today's largest media challenges, from diversity, over AI, VR and AR, to accessibility.

“The media is changing so fast that we want to build these solutions together with the scale-ups and the start-ups. That means that we have to work together in a European context with other public and commercial media players, and together with other accelerators that are here in STADIEM.

Peter De Paepe, Head of VRT Sandbox.

Open call till 28 February 2022

As part of the 2nd open call, European start-ups and scale-ups providing solutions relevant for the media ecosystem can apply and be selected for the STADIEM piloting programme. Successful applicants can benefit from the 4-phase set-up, from finding a match with corporate media partners to piloting their solution on the production floor. On top of that, the selected start-ups and scale-ups can get up to €150,000 of funding to advance its media innovation. The focus areas of this open call are 1) content creation and distribution, 2) archiving, 3) journalism 4.0, 4) content verification and the fight against disinformation, 5) Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media, 6) monetization, and 7) moonshots. Additional information on the 2nd open call and a webinar on the application process can be found on [STADIEM's website](#).

“By providing a specific timeframe within the match phase, the STADIEM programme has really pushed us to focus on securing a partner: the training budget allowed us to access coaching which enabled us to refine our methods and messaging when addressing potential partners.

Jan Spielhoff, FilmChain, one of the scale-ups currently involved in the Develop Phase of STADIEM's programme

STADIEM ON VRT INNOVATION (DECEMBER 2021)

Sign up for STADIEM and fund your media solution

—MARCH 2021

Are you a start-up or scale-up working on next gen media solutions? Do you want to integrate your technology on the production floor, but are you looking for the right connections and resources? Through STADIEM's piloting programme, you will be able to introduce your innovation to an international network and integrate it into a live production environment. You can register now for the first call until the 31st of March.

International piloting programme

The STADIEM project, launched in October 2020, is working on a piloting and acceleration programme to bring together start-ups, scale-ups, investors and media organizations and foster new Next Generation Media solutions. To this end, 7 partners from 6 European countries (Belgium, Norway, Estonia, Germany, Ireland and Switzerland) work together to provide the best possible support on the way to growth. The piloting programme lasts 14 months and consists of 4 phases to introduce start-ups and scaleups to an international network and develop, integrate and test media solutions with a media partner. STADIEM has a budget of €3,86M available and each start-up or SME could receive up to €150,000 for their project.

STADIEM's 4-stage programme

Open Call Webinar

STADIEM hosted a first webinar on the open calls, providing an overview of the project's goals and conditions for participation. You can revisit it [here](#) or register for the [webinar on March 10](#).

“We are excited to make Europe a global leader in media innovation and look forward to not only seize but also create opportunities for media innovation that can have a real impact, both locally and internationally.

Mike Matton, Head of International R&D collaborations, VRT

For all information and tips to apply, you can visit the [Open Call 1](#) and related [FAQs](#) pages of STADIEM's website.

For any specific inquiries, you can contact opencalls@stadiem.eu

STADIEM project is funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement number 957321.

STADIEM ON VRT INNOVATION (MARCH 2021)

